

Accuracy-Latency Tradeoff in Approximate and Delayed Computing as a Game in Satisfaction Form

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Abstract—Approximate and delayed computing have emerged as promising paradigms to offer flexibility in computational accuracy and strategically differentiate tasks between edge and cloud execution to enhance resource utilization. However, these approaches introduce tradeoffs, potentially compromising accuracy on one hand and increasing latency on the other. In this paper, we explore the integration of approximate and delayed computing paradigms within the edge-cloud computing continuum. Users can either offload tasks for approximate computing at the edge or opt for exact but potentially delayed computing at the cloud. In this context, the joint problem of computation task offloading and data compression is formulated and solved as a non-cooperative Game in Satisfaction Form. Each user autonomously determines the amount of task to offload for either computing option and the percentage of data compression for approximate computing, aiming to achieve an acceptable accuracy-latency tradeoff. The formulated game admits a Satisfaction Equilibrium (SE) point, which is concluded using a Reinforcement Learning (RL)-based algorithm. Simulation results demonstrate the performance of the proposed task offloading framework in the achieved accuracy-latency tradeoff compared against different offloading strategies.

Index Terms—Approximate Computing, Edge Computing, Delayed Computing, Satisfaction Games, Reinforcement Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Edge computing plays a critical role in addressing the growing demand for low-latency and high-performance applications by bringing the computational resources closer to the users, thus, enabling faster and more efficient processing [1], [2]. Recently, the advent of *approximate computing* complements edge computing by analyzing a representative sample of data instead of the entire dataset, thus, reducing the computational load, service latency, and energy consumption [3]. To further enhance this, *delayed computing* prioritizes urgent tasks while deferring less critical computations through forwarding to the cloud, thereby optimizing the usage of resources across the computing continuum. In this paper, a novel distributed decision-making framework is introduced, according to which users determine their optimal task offloading and data compression levels by jointly utilizing approximate and delayed

computing within a combined edge-cloud environment. The proposed approach is based on Satisfaction Games, enabling users to efficiently utilize available computing resources while meeting their accuracy and latency requirements.

A. Related Work & Motivation

Task offloading in *edge-cloud computing environments* has gained significant attention for its potential to optimize performance across the computing continuum, with indicative works in [4]–[6], exploring omnidirectional offloading options [7]. A joint communication and task offloading framework is introduced in [4] to minimize the worst-case end-to-end latency in hierarchical edge-cloud systems for Internet of Things (IoT) devices, using alternating optimization and convex approximations. Considering multi-edge multi-cloud networks, a cooperative multi-agent deep reinforcement learning method for efficient task offloading is discussed in [5], specifically targeting to reduce the average latency. An attempt to study the accuracy-latency trade-off in edge-cloud computing is proposed in [6], resulting in significant traffic and latency reductions along with improved accuracy. Last, aiming to jointly optimize energy consumption, delay, and load balancing, an algorithm for task offloading in a collaborative edge-cloud architecture for 6G networks is proposed in [8].

Recently, the paradigms of approximate and delayed computing have been introduced to improve computational efficiency and reduce latency in resource-constrained environments [9]. However, these approaches are examined in isolation, with limited consideration of their integration across the entire edge-cloud computing continuum. The first research stream investigates approximate computing, aiming to optimize efficiency by tolerating reduced accuracy in task execution. An energy-latency-aware task offloading and approximate computing approach is introduced in [10] to optimize the energy consumption and latency in multi-user edge computing systems while in [3] a collaborative Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) and Fully Autonomous Aerial Systems (FAAS) solution is introduced, balancing latency, energy, and accuracy. Regarding delayed computing, several studies explore its potential to enhance system performance by strategically deferring tasks to optimize resource usage (e.g. [11], [12]).

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A delay-optimal task offloading approach is proposed in [11] using integer linear programming to minimize the service time in a multi-tier edge-cloud computing environment.

B. Contributions & Outline

Despite the recent advancements in task offloading and resource optimization techniques, the existing approaches often overlook the integration of approximate and delayed computing to achieve a balanced tradeoff between performance and resource constraints. Additionally, many methods do not fully leverage the users' preferences in the decision-making process, which can lead to sub-optimal resource utilization in edge-cloud computing environments. In this paper, a novel distributed decision-making framework is introduced to enable the users to determine their optimal task offloading and data compression levels by jointly utilizing approximate and delayed computing within a combined edge-cloud environment. The main contributions of this research work are as follows:

- 1) A wireless computing framework with two computation options is introduced: approximate processing at the edge server and delayed, precise computation at the cloud. The tradeoff between task accuracy and latency is systematically analyzed, where the accuracy is modeled as a function of the offloaded proportion of each task.
- 2) The proposed approach quantifies the impact of task distribution on computational performance and latency and targets the optimization of resource allocation in distributed computing environments.
- 3) The joint problem of task partitioning across computation options and task compression is formulated as a non-cooperative satisfaction game. Each user autonomously selects an optimal strategy that satisfies their minimum latency and accuracy requirements. The Satisfaction Equilibrium (SE) ensuring efficient task allocation is determined using a Reinforcement Learning (RL) algorithm.
- 4) Detailed numerical results illustrate the operation and effectiveness of the proposed framework, specifically evaluating the tradeoff between latency, accuracy, and their impact on the system's performance. The proposed framework is also compared to the Nash equilibrium of the problem and other baseline scenarios to quantify its benefits in optimizing the users' task allocation.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a hierarchical two-tier computing architecture, consisting of a set of users $\mathcal{N} = \{1, \dots, n, \dots, N\}$, an edge server, and a cloud server, both of which deliver computational resources and services to the users. The edge server is positioned closer to the users, offering low-latency services, while the cloud provides higher-capacity resources. Each user $n \in \mathcal{N}$ is required to execute K_n distinct computational tasks $\Theta_n = (D_n, \phi_n, t_n, \eta_n)$, where D_n [Bytes] denotes the mean data size of the user's n tasks, ϕ_n [CPU-cycles/Byte] is the mean data processing intensity of each task, and thus the overall task to be processed is represented as $C_n = \phi_n D_n$ [CPU-cycles]. Each user n is constrained by the total time

t_n [sec] available to complete all its tasks, and the minimum acceptable accuracy η_n for task execution.

Two distinct computing options are available to the users:

- (i) **Delayed Computing:** The entire task is transmitted to the edge server, which subsequently forwards it to the cloud for exact computation. This process incurs additional latency due to the extended transmission time required for transferring the task to the cloud.
- (ii) **Approximate Computing:** Part of the tasks' data are compressed by the user before being transmitted to the edge server for faster execution, though this reduces the overall computation accuracy.

The users select one of the computing options for each task, thus, ensuring that each task is fully processed under the chosen method. Let x_n denote the number of tasks user n sends for delayed computing, while the remaining $K_n - x_n$ tasks are sent for approximate computing. Also, let s_n denote the percentage of data D_n of each task Θ_n that the user n decides to send to the edge server for approximate computing.

A. Communication Model

Focusing on the communication model, the wireless network operates in an out-of-band mode, i.e., the wireless access (user-to-edge) and backhaul (edge-to-cloud) transmissions occur on separate frequency bands, denoted by W [Hz] and W_e , respectively. The user-to-edge transmissions use Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) and are multiplexed in the power domain. The channel gain for each user n , G_n , is given by $G_n = \rho d_{n,e}^{-\alpha_e}$, where ρ is the path loss at 1m, α_e is the path loss exponent, and $d_{n,e}$ [m] is the distance between user n and the edge server. The channel gains are sorted in ascending order $G_1 \leq \dots \leq G_n \leq \dots \leq G_N$ and signal decoding follows the Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC) technique. The achievable data rate for user n when offloading to the edge server is given as follows:

$$R_n = W \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{p_n G_n}{\sum_{n'=1}^{n-1} p_{n'} G_{n'} + I_0 W} \right) \quad [\text{bps}], \quad (1)$$

where p_n [Watt] is user's n uplink transmission power and I_0 [dBm/Hz] is the power spectral density of zero-mean Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN). The time overhead for user n when offloading all tasks to the edge server (contingent upon their execution decisions) is defined as follows.

$$T_n^{\text{off}} = \frac{x_n D_n + (K_n - x_n) s_n D_n}{R_n} \quad [\text{sec}]. \quad (2)$$

For task forwarding (applicable only to tasks selected for delayed computing) from the edge to the cloud, the edge server transmits at a fixed power p_e without sensing interference. The channel gain is $G_e = \rho d_{e,c}^{-\alpha_e}$, where $d_{e,c}$ [m] is the Euclidean distance between the edge and cloud server. The achievable data rate is given by:

$$R_e = W_e \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{p_e G_e}{I_0 W_e} \right) \quad [\text{bps}], \quad (3)$$

and the additional time overhead experienced by user n is:

$$T_e^{n,off} = \frac{x_n D_n}{R_e} \quad [\text{sec}]. \quad (4)$$

B. Computing Model

The edge server has a total computing capability F_e [CPU-cycles/sec], which is fairly allocated among the users based on the number and intensity of the computational tasks that they transmit for approximate computing. The server allocates its computing capacity to each user n as follows.

$$F_e^n = \frac{(K_n - x_n) s_n \phi_n D_n}{\sum_{n' \neq n} (K_{n'} - x_{n'}) s_{n'} \phi_{n'} d_{n'}} F_e \quad \left[\frac{\text{CPU-cycles}}{\text{sec}} \right]. \quad (5)$$

The time overhead experienced at the edge server for user n during the approximate computing is derived below.

$$T_e^{n,exec} = \frac{(K_n - x_n) s_n \phi_n D_n}{F_e^n} \quad [\text{sec}]. \quad (6)$$

It is assumed that the cloud server's computing capability far exceeds that of the edge server, thus, its task execution time is negligible.

C. Data Compression - Accuracy Model

As previously mentioned, the tasks selected by each user for approximate computing at the edge server undergo compression to minimize the computational overhead and execution time. However, this preprocessing step affects the final accuracy, as valuable information is lost during the compression. Specifically, as the proportion of data s_n transmitted to the edge server increases, the accuracy of the executed task is expected to improve, approaching that of the exact computing. This relationship can be modeled by the Gompertz function defined as follows [6]:

$$g(s_n) = \alpha e^{be^{cs_n}}, \quad (7)$$

where α is the maximum accuracy achieved by the exact computing and b, c parameters that control how the accuracy grows to its maximum value.

D. Accuracy-Latency Tradeoff Utility Function Model

In this section, we define a utility function that captures each user's satisfaction level within the system. Each user has specific latency and accuracy requirements for executing their tasks. Meeting both requirements results in positive utility while failing to meet either leads to dissatisfaction and negative utility. Thus, the user's utility is expressed as follows.

$$u_n(x_n, s_n, \mathbf{x}_{-n}, \mathbf{s}_{-n}) = \begin{cases} -\left(\frac{t_n - T_n^{total}}{t_n}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{g(s_n) - \eta_n}{\eta_n}\right), \\ \text{if } t_n \leq T_n^{total} \text{ and } g(s_n) \leq \eta_n, \\ \left(\frac{t_n - T_n^{total}}{t_n}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{g(s_n) - \eta_n}{\eta_n}\right), \text{ else,} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where $T_n^{total} = T_n^{off} + T_e^{n,off} + T_e^{n,exec}$ is the total latency of user n for the execution of all of its tasks and $\mathbf{x}_{-n} = (x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_{n+1}, \dots, x_N)$, $\mathbf{s}_{-n} = (s_1, \dots, s_{n-1}, s_{n+1}, \dots, s_N)$ are the actions of all users except for user n .

III. COMPUTATION TASK OFFLOADING & COMPRESSION AS A GAME IN SATISFACTION FORM

Each user aims to optimize their task execution to meet their minimum performance requirements. Thus, the goal of the users is to determine an optimal task allocation strategy, x_n , across two execution options and the proportion of tasks, s_n , assigned for approximate computing and offloaded to the edge server after compression. By tuning these parameters, the users can balance the minimization of their latency and the maximization of their processing accuracy. This problem is addressed as a non-cooperative game in satisfaction form.

A. Satisfaction Game Formulation and Equilibrium

The non-cooperative game among the users can be represented by the following tuple:

$$\mathcal{G} = [\mathcal{N}, \{\mathcal{A}_n\}_{n \in \mathcal{N}}, \{f_n\}_{n \in \mathcal{N}}], \quad (9)$$

where \mathcal{N} is the set of users, $\mathcal{A}_n = \{(x_n, s_n) | x_n \in [0, K_n], x_n \in \mathbb{Z}, s_n \in [0, 1]\}$ is the user's n action space, and $f_n(a_{-n}) = \{a_n \in \mathcal{A}_n | u_n(a_n) \geq 0\}$ defines the requirements set, i.e. the set of actions of user n that satisfy both its minimum requirements. The outcome of a satisfaction game is the Satisfaction Equilibrium (SE).

Definition 1 (Satisfaction Equilibrium (SE)). *An action profile $\mathbf{a}^* = (a_1^*, \dots, a_n^*, \dots, a_N^*)$ is an SE for game \mathcal{G} if $a_n^* \in f_n(\mathbf{a}_{-n}^*), \forall n \in \mathcal{N}$.*

Algorithm 1 Satisfaction Equilibrium Learning Algorithm

- 1: Set $\tau = 0$;
 - 2: Initialize probabilities $\pi_{n,l_n}(0) = \frac{1}{A_n}, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}, l_n \in \mathcal{L}_n$;
 - 3: **for** each $n \in \mathcal{N}$ **do**
 - 4: Select an action $a_n(0) \sim \pi_n(0)$;
 - 5: **end for**
 - 6: **while** $\exists n \in \mathcal{N}$ such that $u_n(\tau) < 0$ **do**
 - 7: **for** each $n \in \mathcal{N}$ **do**
 - 8: Update probability $\pi_n(\tau + 1)$ based on Eq. 10;
 - 9: $a_n(\tau + 1) = \begin{cases} a_n(\tau), & \text{if } u_n(\tau) \geq 0 \\ z \sim \pi_n(\tau + 1), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$
 - 10: **end for**
 - 11: Update $\tau = \tau + 1$;
 - 12: **end while**
-

B. Learning Satisfaction Equilibrium

A Reinforcement Learning algorithm is introduced to determine the SEs of the game G in a fully distributed manner [13]. In this framework, the users have complete knowledge of their potential actions and the recent actions of others, allowing them to assess their utility values and ensure their minimum requirements for positive satisfaction are met. The RL algorithm runs through multiple iterations τ . For analysis simplicity, each user's action set \mathcal{A}_n is indexed by $l_n \in \mathcal{L}_n = \{1, \dots, a_n, \dots, A_n\}$, where the l_n -th action of user n is a_{n,l_n} .

In each iteration τ , each user n selects an action based on a probabilistic distribution $\pi_n(\tau) = (\pi_{n,1}(\tau), \dots, \pi_{n,l_n}(\tau), \dots, \pi_{n,A_n}(\tau))$ over its action space. At the first iteration, this distribution is uniform, i.e., $\pi_{n,l_n}(0) = \frac{1}{A_n} \forall n \in \mathcal{N}, l_n \in \mathcal{L}_n$ to ensure equal likelihood of

Fig. 1: Pure operation of the proposed framework.

action selection. In subsequent iterations, each user evaluates if their requirements are satisfied (i.e., achieving positive utility). If satisfied, the probability distribution remains unchanged. If not, it is updated according to the following rule:

$$\pi_{n,l_n}(\tau+1) = \begin{cases} \pi_{n,l_n}(\tau), & \text{if } u_n(\tau) \geq 0, \\ g(\pi_{n,l_n}(\tau)), & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where $g(\pi_{n,l_n}(\tau)) = \pi_{n,l_n}(\tau) + \lambda_\tau r_{n,\tau} (\mathbb{1}_{\{a_n(\tau)=a_{n,l_n}\}} - \pi_{n,l_n}(\tau))$. Within this rule $a_n(\tau)$ corresponds to the action selected by user n at iteration τ , λ_τ the learning rate of the algorithm, while $r_{n,\tau}$ is the reward function for the RL mechanism. The objective of this reward is to increase the selection probabilities of actions that enhance the user's utility, thus boosting the chances of achieving positive satisfaction:

$$r_{n,\tau} = \frac{u_n^{max} - u_n(\tau)}{2 \cdot u_n^{max}}, \quad (11)$$

where u_n^{max} is the maximum utility value user n can achieve. The RL algorithm is presented in Algorithm 1. Its complexity depends solely on the number of iterations for convergence, with each step involving $O(1)$ algebraic computations, executed in a fully distributed and parallel manner.

IV. EVALUATION & RESULTS

In this section, a thorough simulation-based evaluation is provided to demonstrate the performance and efficiency of the proposed framework. We consider a two-layer edge-cloud network, consisting of an edge server, which lies 500 m away from a cloud server, and $N = 10$ users randomly distributed around them. The rest of the simulation parameters are set as follows, unless otherwise explicitly stated: $K_n = 10$, $t_n = 1.2$ sec, $\eta_n = 0.85$, $p_n = 0.1$ Watt, $\forall n \in \mathcal{N}$, $D_n \in [0.3 + 0.2n]_{n=1}^{10}$ MBytes, $\phi_n \in [100 + 100n]_{n=1}^{10}$ CPU-cycles/Byte, $I_0 = -174$ dbm/Hz, $p_e = 0.1$ Watt, $W = 5$ MHz, $W_e = 1$ MHz, $\rho = 1$, $a_e = 2.5$, $F_e = 5 \cdot 10^{11}$ CPU-cycles/sec, $\alpha = 1$, $b = -1$ and $c = -3$. Additionally, each user's action set consists of 100 compression levels, which are defined within the feasible range of $[0.01, 1]$ in steps of 0.01. For statistical purposes, the results presented in the following have been averaged over 100 different initializations corresponding to different channel gain realizations.

A. Pure Operation

This section studies the pure operational characteristics of the proposed framework. Fig. 1a demonstrates for each user the number of tasks x_n offloaded to the cloud and the portion s_n of tasks' data used for approximate computing. Fig. 1b – 1c show the convergence of the RL-based algorithm determining the SE regarding the computing tasks' latency and accuracy, respectively. It is noted that as the user ID increases, both the mean data size D_n and the task intensity ϕ_n increase, resulting in a heavier overall task computational burden. Also, identical latency and accuracy constraints are considered for all users.

The results reveal that as the user's ID increases and the tasks become more intensive, fewer tasks are offloaded to the cloud to meet the user's latency constraints and minimize the transmission time. The data offloaded for approximate computing are more compressed, i.e., a smaller portion s_n of tasks are offloaded (Fig. 1a). Nevertheless, all users successfully satisfy their latency and accuracy constraints, while the lower ID users achieve lower latency and higher accuracy due to their less intensive tasks (Fig. 1b – 1c), where user IDs are presented in the legend of Fig. 1c for reference.

B. Accuracy-Latency Tradeoff

This section analyzes the accuracy-latency tradeoff under the proposed framework, considering different values of accuracy and latency constraints. Fig. 2a – 2e present the users' mean experienced latency in processing their tasks, the mean accuracy of tasks executed with approximate computing, the mean portion s_n of task data transmitted for approximate computing, the percentage of users satisfying both latency and accuracy constraints, and the mean number of tasks offloaded to the cloud (x_n) for delayed computing, respectively. The experiment is performed considering identical users, where $K_n = 10$, $D_n = 0.5$ MBytes, $\phi_n = 100$ CPU-cycles/Byte with the same latency and accuracy constraints.

The results reveal that as the latency constraints relax, more tasks are offloaded to the cloud (Fig. 2e), increasing the overall execution time (Fig. 2a) and reducing the data compression, i.e., higher s_n (Fig. 2c), which leads to improved accuracy (Fig. 2b). Thus, the percentage of satisfied users increases (Fig. 2d) as meeting their latency constraints becomes easier. In contrast, when the accuracy constraints become stricter, more

Fig. 2: Accuracy-latency tradeoff under the proposed framework.

tasks are sent to the cloud for exact computing, resulting in longer execution times and increased data compression (lower s_n). However, the percentage of satisfied users decreases due to the challenges of achieving high accuracy.

C. Scalability Analysis

To analyze the scalability of the proposed framework, two scenarios are generated. We consider the base case of $N = 10$ users with $K_n = 10$, $t_n = 3$ sec and $\eta_n = 80\% \forall n \in \mathcal{N}$ and expand upon this by increasing the number of users in two ways: (i) Homogeneous: All added users have the same task size of $D_n = 0.5$ MBytes, and (ii) Heterogeneous: Each newly introduced user has a larger task by 0.1 MBytes starting from $D_1 = 0.5$ Mbytes for the initial user. Fig. 3a – 3b illustrate the mean experienced latency by the users, the mean accuracy achieved with the approximate computing, and the percentage of satisfied users for an increasing number of users in the horizontal axis, under the two scalability scenarios. The results show that in both scalability scenarios, increasing the number of users results in higher latency and reduced accuracy (Fig. 3a). The increase in latency is attributed to the increased interference during task offloading, while the decrease in accuracy occurs since the edge server’s resources are shared among more users. This resource sharing compels users to compress their data more (resulting in lower s_n) to meet the system’s constraints. In the Heterogeneous scenario, latency is even higher and accuracy is further reduced due to the increased system demand. Furthermore, the inclusion of more users makes it more challenging for them to meet their constraints, leading to a lower percentage of satisfied users (Fig. 3b). This decline is more pronounced in the Heterogeneous scenario due to the users’ heterogeneous characteristics.

Fig. 3: Scalability analysis.

D. Comparative Analysis

Subsequently, a comparative evaluation of the proposed framework is performed against five alternative scenarios: (i) Only Time and (ii) Only Accuracy: Users’ decisions (s_n, x_n) are based on a satisfaction game with their utility focusing solely on time, and on accuracy, respectively; (iii): Only Approximate: All users transmit their tasks to the edge server ($x_n = 0$) for approximate computing, with compression s_n determined by a satisfaction game; (iv): Only Delay: All users transmit their tasks to the cloud server for delayed computing ($x_n = K_n$ for all users, with s_n not applicable); and (v) Nash Equilibrium (NE): Users’ decisions are derived via a normal-form game with identical utility functions, where each user aims to maximize its utility rather than meeting its constraints.

Fig. 4 illustrates the mean experienced latency and accuracy of users’ tasks across the various comparative scenarios, while Table I summarizes the percentage of users meeting both time and accuracy constraints for each scenario. Additionally, Table II provides a statistical comparison of our proposed framework against the NE scenario, focusing on the mean value and mean standard deviation of the experienced latency and accuracy.

The results reveal that the Only Time scenario results in

Fig. 4: Comparative analysis.

lower latency compared to the proposed framework, as it focuses exclusively on time constraints. However, this comes at the cost of reduced mean accuracy. In contrast, the Only Accuracy scenario improves accuracy but increases the experienced latency. The Only Approximate scenario, which leverages the nearby edge server, significantly reduces latency, but since all tasks are approximated, it results in lower mean accuracy. The Only Delay scenario achieves optimal accuracy, as all tasks are executed with exact computing, but incurs high latency. Finally, the NE scenario produces similar time and accuracy values to the proposed framework (SE), with the SE achieving higher mean accuracy at the expense of slightly increased mean latency (Fig. 4). Notably, the standard deviation for both time and accuracy is lower in SE (Table II), indicating a more balanced performance across users.

Focusing on the percentage of users meeting both time and accuracy constraints, the proposed solution consistently satisfies both constraints for all users. In the Only Time scenario, accuracy satisfaction drops significantly as users prioritize reducing latency. Conversely, the Only Accuracy scenario yields a reduction in time constraint satisfaction. The Only Approximate scenario generally meets the constraints, but the mean accuracy is lower than the proposed solution. The Only Delay scenario fails to satisfy the time constraints for nearly 40% of the users due to the extra transmission time, although accuracy is consistently maintained through exact computing. Finally, the NE solution exhibits reduced user satisfaction percentages due to competition among users.

V. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

In conclusion, this paper introduced a novel distributed decision-making framework that enables users to optimize their task offloading and data compression in a combined edge-cloud environment, where approximate and delayed computing options are available. The joint problem of task partitioning and compression was formulated as a non-cooperative game, allowing the users to autonomously select strategies that satisfy their latency and accuracy requirements while achieving a Satisfaction Equilibrium for efficient task allocation. Numerical results demonstrated the framework’s effectiveness in optimizing resource allocation, significantly outperforming traditional Nash equilibrium approaches and other baseline scenarios. Part of our current and future work involves jointly considering radio resource allocation during task offloading and forwarding across wireless edge-cloud infrastructures.

TABLE I: Percentage of satisfied users.

Method	Latency Constraint (%)	Accuracy Constraint (%)
Proposed	100	100
Only Time	99.97	36.4
Only Accuracy	74.6	99.91
Only Approximate	98.92	99.43
Only Delay	62.5	100
NE	87.64	99.69

TABLE II: SE-NE comparison.

Solution	SE	NE
Mean Latency	0.832	0.776
STD Latency	0.386	0.415
Mean Accuracy	0.954	0.943
STD Accuracy	0.028	0.038

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